

All									Generalist-Generalist					Generalist-Specialist					Specialist-Specialist							
	Clownfish richness	Host richness	Num. generalist	Num. specialists	Co-occurrence proportion	Coexistence proportion	Ecological overlap	Host-specific overlap		Num. of interactions	Co-occurrence proportion	Coexistence proportion	Ecological overlap	Host-specific overlap		Num. of interactions	Co-occurrence proportion	Coexistence proportion	Ecological overlap	Host-specific overlap		Num. of interactions	Co-occurrence proportion	Coexistence proportion	Ecological overlap	Host-specific overlap
Andaman	5.381	3.489	0.924	4.457	0.822	0.435	0.271	0.108	Andaman	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Andaman	4.254	0.338	0.632	0.550	0.177	Andaman	8.074	0.662	0.368	0.132	0.073
Central Indian Ocean Islands	3.705	2.826	0.965	2.739	0.875	0.998	0.572	0.402	Central Indian Ocean Islands	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Central Indian Ocean Islands	2.664	0.539	0.538	0.640	0.326	Central Indian Ocean Islands	2.583	0.461	0.462	0.505	0.477
East Central Australian Shelf	2.742	5.689	1.000	1.742	0.828	1.000	0.556	0.281	East Central Australian Shelf	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	East Central Australian Shelf	1.742	0.753	0.753	0.613	0.311	East Central Australian Shelf	0.742	0.247	0.247	0.442	0.221
Eastern Coral Triangle	8.101	6.997	5.481	2.619	0.843	0.771	0.499	0.214	Eastern Coral Triangle	12.978	0.424	0.499	0.610	0.328	Eastern Coral Triangle	15.028	0.507	0.477	0.460	0.145	Eastern Coral Triangle	2.342	0.070	0.024	0.173	0.059
Java Transitional	5.546	6.677	2.769	2.777	0.873	0.644	0.432	0.201	Java Transitional	2.550	0.223	0.328	0.721	0.341	Java Transitional	7.835	0.580	0.350	0.230	0.054	Java Transitional	2.713	0.197	0.323	0.750	0.500
Marshall Gilbert and Ellis Islands	2.000	3.950	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.651	0.470	Marshall Gilbert and Ellis Islands	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Marshall Gilbert and Ellis Islands	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.651	0.470	Marshall Gilbert and Ellis Islands	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Northeast Australian Shelf	6.811	7.883	5.813	0.999	0.958	0.902	0.746	0.332	Northeast Australian Shelf	14.304	0.697	0.771	0.834	0.417	Northeast Australian Shelf	5.810	0.303	0.229	0.526	0.118	Northeast Australian Shelf	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Northwest Australian Shelf	5.297	4.593	2.749	2.548	0.812	0.772	0.417	0.200	Northwest Australian Shelf	2.605	0.207	0.271	0.654	0.394	Northwest Australian Shelf	7.327	0.630	0.665	0.426	0.152	Northwest Australian Shelf	2.241	0.162	0.064	0.151	0.151
Sahul Shelf	5.983	6.136	2.312	3.671	0.758	0.838	0.385	0.154	Sahul Shelf	1.942	0.103	0.126	0.341	0.143	Sahul Shelf	8.849	0.521	0.542	0.386	0.130	Sahul Shelf	5.122	0.375	0.332	0.403	0.207
Somali Arabian	2.000	2.913	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.646	0.507	Somali Arabian	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Somali Arabian	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.646	0.507	Somali Arabian	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
South China Sea	2.699	1.965	0.000	2.699	0.800	1.000	0.480	0.416	South China Sea	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	South China Sea	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	South China Sea	2.399	1.000	1.000	0.480	0.416
South Kuroshio	3.289	1.906	2.781	0.508	0.655	0.831	0.354	0.191	South Kuroshio	2.609	0.704	0.823	0.599	0.333	South Kuroshio	1.320	0.296	0.177	0.110	0.049	South Kuroshio	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Sunda Shelf	7.093	9.676	2.920	4.172	0.792	0.533	0.296	0.098	Sunda Shelf	2.858	0.134	0.256	0.739	0.297	Sunda Shelf	12.363	0.567	0.628	0.346	0.079	Sunda Shelf	6.956	0.300	0.116	0.089	0.068
Tropical Northwestern Pacific	3.898	4.884	2.942	0.956	0.956	1.000	0.811	0.524	Tropical Northwestern Pacific	2.884	0.519	0.519	0.825	0.612	Tropical Northwestern Pacific	2.855	0.481	0.481	0.797	0.435	Tropical Northwestern Pacific	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Tropical Southwestern Pacific	7.330	5.068	6.397	0.932	0.849	0.975	0.670	0.386	Tropical Southwestern Pacific	17.678	0.750	0.760	0.663	0.407	Tropical Southwestern Pacific	6.098	0.250	0.240	0.691	0.324	Tropical Southwestern Pacific	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Warm Temperate Northwest Pacific	2.000	3.758	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.786	0.154	Warm Temperate Northwest Pacific	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Warm Temperate Northwest Pacific	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.786	0.154	Warm Temperate Northwest Pacific	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Western Coral Triangle	8.326	9.145	3.902	4.424	0.874	0.612	0.435	0.138	Western Coral Triangle	5.736	0.201	0.316	0.779	0.270	Western Coral Triangle	17.509	0.557	0.562	0.437	0.097	Western Coral Triangle	8.204	0.242	0.122	0.223	0.139
Western Indian Ocean	5.345	7.316	2.846	2.500	0.816	0.966	0.631	0.259	Western Indian Ocean	2.742	0.233	0.249	0.703	0.326	Western Indian Ocean	7.336	0.616	0.596	0.604	0.182	Western Indian Ocean	2.160	0.151	0.155	0.637	0.422